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THE MOTIF OF DREAMS IN PSYCHOLOGICAL REALISM

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Annotation. *This article provides a well-structured and informative overview of the use of dreams as a motif in psychological realist literature. It effectively connects the literary technique with the psychological concept of dreams as a window into the unconscious mind. The use of specific examples and references strengthens the argument and clarifies the points made.*

Keywords: *dream, psychological realism, literary technique, motif, inner state, psyche*

МОТИВ СНОВИДЕНИЯ В ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ РЕАЛИЗМЕ

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Аннотация. *В этой статье представлен хорошо структурированный и информативный обзор использования снов как мотива в литературе психологического реализма. Он эффективно соединяет литературную технику с психологической концепцией снов как окна в бессознательное. Использование конкретных примеров и ссылок усиливает аргумент и проясняет высказанные моменты.*

Ключевые слова: *сон, психологический реализм, литературный прием, мотив, внутреннее состояние, психика.*

The human mind, in its vast and uncharted territories, has long captivated writers, particularly those exploring the depths of human experience within the realm of psychological realism. Psychological Realism is the literary genre that delves on the internal life of the characters. Realism is lent to the text through a

focus on the thoughts and motivations of the characters rather than on their occupations and external settings alone. [1] In this exploration, dreams emerge as a powerful motif, offering unique glimpses into the hidden aspects of the psyche.

Recent studies suggest that dream content may offer a unique window into the cognitive and emotional processes of the unconscious mind, potentially serving as a valuable tool for understanding psychological well-being and promoting self-awareness. Sigmund Freud's psychoanalysis significantly influenced the development of psychological realism. His theories placed emphasis on the unconscious mind, a realm filled with desires, conflicts, and traumas often hidden from conscious awareness. Dreams, according to Freud, were "the royal road to the unconscious," allowing indirect access to repressed thoughts and emotions. [2]

Throughout history, dreams have been recognized as a source of creative inspiration and have been incorporated into literary works to provide insights into the realm of the subconscious and the complexities of human experience. Writers embraced this concept, weaving dreams into their narratives to illuminate the internal landscapes of their characters. In Fyodor Dostoevsky's "Crime and Punishment", Raskolnikov's recurrent dream of a horse being beaten to death symbolizes his own guilt and internal turmoil. Similarly, James Joyce's "Ulysses" utilizes Leopold Bloom's dream sequences to unveil his anxieties, desires, and unresolved childhood issues.

In psychological realism, the motif of dreams goes beyond literal interpretation and serves as a multifaceted tool for exploring various depths of the human psyche. While some dreams in psychological realism serve as straightforward reflections of the character's inner state, others are more symbolic and open to interpretation. Dreams can depict fragmented memories, anxieties, desires, and unresolved conflicts that lurk beneath the surface of conscious awareness. They offer indirect access to these hidden contents, allowing characters to confront and potentially understand them better. In Virginia Woolf's "Mrs. Dalloway", Clarissa's dream of a man falling from a tower is ambiguous, yet hints at her fear of aging and mortality. Dreams can also function as catalysts for personal growth and transformation. In Toni Morrison's "Beloved", Sethe's dreams about her deceased daughter, Beloved, force her to confront her repressed trauma and ultimately move towards emotional healing. Beyond individual psychology, dreams in psychological realism can also reflect broader social and

cultural anxieties. In Kate Chopin's "The Awakening", Edna Pontellier's dreams of birds symbolize her yearning for freedom and escape from societal constraints.

The device of the dream is effective, however, only where it is an integral of the work and not merely an appendage or a flight of fancy. There must be a build-up of tension to the moment of the dream; there must be a line of thought which is released, revealed, or explained in the dream. The term "catharsis" may be applied here as a literary technique as well as a psychological principle. The dream is kept within the context of the work also by means of a controlled symbolism, each image having its counterpart within the range of the story or of the experience of the character as he is presented in the story. [3]

The motif of dreams in psychological realism extends beyond mere plot devices. By delving into the oneiric world, authors offer profound insights into the complexities of the human psyche, exploring hidden desires, repressed traumas, and the potential for personal transformation.

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